

THE 1992 UN WATER CONVENTION

BENEFITS AND GUIDANCE TO ACCESSION

COOPERATION FOR
SHARED
WATER FUTURES

RIVERS ARE A NATIONAL
RIGHT NOT A SHARED
OBLIGATION

Equitable & Reasonable
Use

Protection & Sustainable
Management

Cooperation &
Information Exchange

Monitoring
& Assessment

Institutional Arrangements &
Capacity Building

The 1992 UN Water Convention: Benefits and Guidance to Accession

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Preface

Due to the uncertainty of climate change and increasing water stress worldwide, managing shared water resources effectively and sustainably has become a priority. Coordinated water governance mechanisms are required to ensure equitable and reasonable use of transboundary water systems. Cooperation over transboundary waters is an essential means of demonstrating regional stability between riparian countries. A practical and efficient collaboration framework has been established under the 1992 United Nations Convention on the Protection and Use of Transboundary Watercourses and International Lakes (UN Water Convention).

A structured overview of the Convention has been developed in this document to demonstrate the cooperative approach to shared water resources and the Convention's role in addressing challenges posed by growing water demand, climate change, and water scarcity. This document also highlights the key benefits that parties gain under the Convention, including strengthened institutional capacity, enhanced cooperation mechanisms, and access to international support networks.

Moreover, the document illustrates the key obligations undertaken by parties under the Convention, the procedural pathway for the accession process, and explains the actors assisting in the accession journey. For countries evaluating accession, the experience of Iraq has been explained to highlight practical considerations and lessons.

Designed for policymakers, practitioners, and stakeholders engaged in water governance, this document serves as both a reference and a practical guide. It seeks to contribute to a broader understanding of the value of transboundary water cooperation and to support countries in exploring pathways toward more sustainable and collaborative water management.

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1. The Water Convention (Convention on the Protection and Use of Transboundary Watercourses and International Lakes of 1992)

The Convention is a global multilateral agreement designed to improve the protection and management of transboundary waters (both surface and groundwater) through provisions on prevention, control, and reduction of impacts on water resources. The Convention does not replace specific bilateral and multilateral agreements on transboundary basins and aquifers. Instead, it fosters the establishment and implementation of such agreements, as well as their further development.

The Water Convention is one of the most important international legal frameworks for transboundary water cooperation. Opened for signature in Helsinki on 17 March 1992, it was originally negotiated as a regional instrument for the United Nations Economic Commission for Europe (UNECE) region. Then, in 2003, the Convention was amended to allow accession by all United Nations Member States, regardless of their location. The amendment entered into force in 2013, and the Convention's global opening has been fully operational since 2016.

The Convention's main strength is that it combines clear legal obligations with practical mechanisms for implementation. It promotes the equitable and reasonable use of shared waters, the prevention and control of transboundary impacts, regular exchange of information, joint monitoring, consultation, and cooperation through appropriate institutional arrangements. It also provides a flexible framework that can be adapted to different geographic, hydrological and political contexts. As a result, the Water Convention is valuable not only as a treaty, but also as a practical guide for strengthening cooperation, building trust, reducing the risk of disputes and improving the long-term governance of shared water resources.

A growing list of countries have come to appreciate the Water Convention's benefits. Since the Convention's global opening in 2016, countries from Africa, the Middle East, Latin America and Asia have joined: Chad and Senegal (2018); Ghana (2020); Guinea-Bissau and Togo (2021); Cameroon (2022); Gambia, Iraq, Namibia, Nigeria and Panama (2023); Cote d'Ivoire, Zambia and Zimbabwe (2024). Bangladesh and Sierra Leone are the most recent Parties that joined the Water Convention in 2025.

Figure 1 below shows the Water Convention Parties from 1994 to 2025 [1]. Figure 2 illustrates the achievements of parties to the Water Convention through transboundary cooperation [1].

Figure 1 The number of countries that joined the Water Convention from 1994 to 2025 [1]

Figure 2 The Achievements of Parties to the Water Convention Through Transboundary Cooperation

[1, 2]

2. What are the key benefits of international collaboration on transboundary waters?

Transboundary water cooperation is essential for managing shared waters in an integrated and sustainable manner. It has the potential to generate numerous significant benefits for all riparian states. These benefits span environmental, economic, political, and social dimensions, transforming a potential source of conflict into a foundation for shared prosperity and stability. Firstly, it is a cornerstone of peace and stability, as formal cooperation builds trust through transparent data-sharing and joint institutions, effectively preventing conflicts. This collaboration directly enhances water security for all riparian states by enabling coordinated management of floods and droughts, leading to avoided economic losses and saved lives. Environmentally, it is indispensable for protecting entire riverine ecosystems and controlling pollution across borders, ensuring the long-term health of the basin. Economically, joint action unlocks significant efficiencies—from cost-sharing on infrastructure to optimizing uses like hydropower and irrigation—making the entire region more attractive for investment. Finally, these efforts yield direct social dividends, including improved public health from cleaner water, greater food security, and strengthened institutional capacity through shared knowledge and technology. In essence, transboundary water cooperation is a pragmatic strategy that generates positive-sum outcomes, where collaborative management creates greater value, resilience, and well-being for every nation involved than any could achieve alone.

3. What can the Convention do in response to water resources scarcity, growing water demand, climate change, and pollution problems?

The Blue Peace Middle East (BPME) countries face profound and interlinked water challenges. These include increasing water scarcity and competition for resources, the escalating impacts of climate change on hydrological cycles, widespread pollution from agricultural, industrial, and municipal sources, and the degradation of ecosystems that depend on water security. These challenges are compounded by their transboundary nature, as shared basins require coordinated management to prevent conflict and unlock cooperative benefits.

To help its Parties address these complex issues directly, the UN Water Convention implements a dynamic and practical program of work. This program translates the Convention's legal framework into concrete action through specific thematic areas, including water and adaptation to climate change, water quality and pollution prevention, and the water-food-energy-ecosystem nexus. Its methodology is intensely operational, combining technical, legal, and policy support. This involves developing dedicated guidance and tools (such as on transboundary water allocation or nexus assessments), organizing systematic exchange of experiences, and convening countries around shared challenges through dedicated Task Forces. Crucially, the Convention facilitates on-the-ground implementation by supporting pilot projects in river basins, often in cooperation with regional partners, to test and demonstrate integrated management approaches.

4. Advantages of Becoming a Party to the Water Convention

4.1. Promote Regional Cooperation

Joining the Convention strengthens collaboration with neighboring countries on shared water resources. This cooperation is essential for effectively managing transboundary watercourses and groundwater resources, particularly given the limited water resources in the MENA region.

4.2. Sustainable Water-Resources Management

The Convention promotes the sustainable and equitable use of transboundary waters. Based on its principles, the Parties can take steps towards implementing more effective management practices that conserve water resources and balance all water needs, which are vital for ecosystem protection, environmental sustainability, and meeting the population's needs. While guidance on specific aspects like water allocation in a transboundary context has been developed to ensure equity, the Convention's framework emphasizes a holistic approach. This includes methodologies such as the water-energy-food-ecosystem nexus, which helps Parties coordinate multi-sectoral uses and protect vital ecosystems in their shared basins [3]. This approach would also promote International Water Resources Management (IWRM).

4.3. Exchange of information

A cornerstone of the Convention is its establishment of a robust framework for the systematic exchange of information, which is fundamental for building trust and enabling effective joint management. Therefore, the Convention provides the framework for day-to-day cooperation, including through the exchange of information and data, consultations, early warning and alarm systems, mutual assistance, and other procedures. Article 6 creates a general obligation for Parties to exchange information on all Convention-related issues. In contrast, Article 13 obliges explicitly Riparian Parties to exchange reasonably available data and information on their shared waters upon request. This flow of data, covering hydrology, pollution, planned measures, and more, is indispensable for informed decision-making, conflict prevention, and cooperative action. The Convention also provides, in Article 8, necessary clarifications to ensure this exchange respects national legal systems concerning specific safeguards.

4.4. Pollution Prevention and Control

The Convention establishes obligations to prevent, control, and reduce pollution in transboundary waters. It outlines measures to address pollution at its source, aligning with environmental protection needs.

4.5. Research and development

The Convention encourages research, development, and the exchange of environmentally sound technologies, boosting technical capacity.

4.6. Improved transboundary groundwater management

The Water Convention covers all transboundary surface and groundwater, including both confined and unconfined aquifers. The Convention requires the conclusion of specific agreements on transboundary water. It can facilitate the development of aquifer-specific agreements by providing tailored assistance to this end, potentially based on the Model Provisions on Transboundary Groundwaters, which were developed within the Convention's framework [4]. Several tools and activities can further support the Party in better managing its groundwater resources: Updated Strategies for Monitoring and Assessment of

Transboundary Rivers, Lakes and Groundwaters, and ongoing activities on conjunctive management of surface and groundwater [5].

4.7. Improvement of water resources management at the domestic level

Accession to the Convention presents an occasion to review and strengthen national water policies and practices, enhance intersectoral cooperation and stakeholder participation in water resources management, and introduce new preventive measures at the national level for the optimal utilization and protection of transboundary waters and related ecosystems. In other words, accession can prompt a re-boost of domestic water management and governance frameworks and thus improve the status of water bodies within the national borders and beyond.

4.8. Legal Framework for Dispute prevention and resolution

The Convention provides a comprehensive framework for preventing and resolving disputes related to transboundary water management by promoting bilateral and multilateral cooperation among riparian parties. It mandates that these parties enter into agreements to define their mutual relations concerning the prevention, control, and reduction of transboundary impacts, and establish joint institutions to manage their shared resources, thereby establishing a legal and institutional framework for the peaceful prevention and resolution of disputes. Article 22(1) of the Water Convention provides the core procedural obligation: Parties must seek a solution through negotiation or any other peaceful means of their choice, such as mediation, inquiry, conciliation, arbitration, or judicial settlement. Among the supportive mechanisms available, the Convention has a standing body, the Implementation Committee, which offers a simple, non-confrontational, non-adversarial, transparent, and supportive mechanism to facilitate and support the implementation of and compliance with the Convention and prevent and address any differences in its implementation between Parties.

4.9. The development of bilateral or multilateral agreements and the establishment of Joint Bodies

The Convention specifies the establishment of joint bodies tasked with various responsibilities, including monitoring programs and conducting environmental impact assessments related to transboundary waters, which is an obligation under the Convention. The Convention also prompts the entering into bilateral or multilateral agreements or other arrangements.

4.10. Remarks on risks and financial obligations

Acceding to the Convention has no seen disadvantages or risks. From the financial point of view, the Convention does not legally require Parties to financially contribute to its funding. However, there's an expectation that all Parties do so. A discussion is ongoing to define a process towards a more sustainable and predictable financing mechanism for the Water Convention's work (see the decision adopted by the meeting of the Parties at its 10th session in October 2024).

4.11. Support from the community of Parties

Parties to the Convention mutually assist each other within the Convention's framework and through direct bilateral cooperation. The experience of new Parties has clearly shown that they have benefited greatly from the assistance of experienced Parties in the form of twinning or development cooperation, which has helped them advance in implementing the Water Convention. New Parties have also benefited from assistance and financial support by the international community, which has recognized their commitment to cooperation. For instance, Senegal, Guinea-Bissau, and Gambia (all new Parties) and Mauritania (country in accession) have been able to mobilize about 14 million USD from different sources (World Bank, GEF, EU, and Italy) to strengthen their cooperation around their shared aquifer.

4.12. Capacity Building

The Convention enhances the institutional capacity for managing water resources through all activities organized under its program of work, including:

- a) Monitoring programs and data sharing: facilitating cooperation on monitoring transboundary waters.
- b) Development of agreements and establishment of joint bodies: supporting legal frameworks for transboundary cooperation.
- c) Improvement of water quality: addressing pollution issues in shared water bodies.
- d) Intersectoral water-food-energy-ecosystem coordination: promoting integrated management approaches across sectors.
- e) Water allocation: ensuring equitable distribution in a transboundary context.
- f) Conjunctive management of surface and groundwater: encouraging holistic management practices.
- g) Ecosystems conservation: protecting biodiversity in transboundary basins.
- h) Climate change adaptation: enhancing resilience against climate impacts through cooperative measures.
- i) Financing cooperation: Exploring potential funding for joint projects
- j) Reporting: tracking progress towards sustainable development goals related to water management.

For detailed information on these activities, see (2025-2027 programme of work) [6].

4.13. Support to disaster risk reduction and climate action

The Convention and its activities, in particular, all the work carried out on water and climate, support the strengthening of resilience at the national and regional levels, as well as efforts to adapt to climate change and reduce disaster risk, particularly the risks associated with water-related disasters. Numerous guidance documents can support any Party's efforts in mainstreaming water into climate change adaptation and mitigation (Guidance on Water and Adaptation to Climate Change, Implementation Guide for Addressing Water-Related Disasters and Transboundary Cooperation), as well as the work of a dedicated Task Force on Water and Climate and the Global Network of Basins working on Climate Change Adaptation [7].

4.14. Recognition by the International Community

Accession shows the Party's commitment to international norms, enhancing its standing among other nations and organizations. Increased recognition can potentially lead to more international support and partnerships in water management initiatives, as well as attract funds from donors. The work on financing transboundary water cooperation and basin development under the Convention can further support the new Party in identifying and mobilizing financial resources from various sources to enhance transboundary water cooperation and management.

4.15. Developed Institutional Platform

Participation enables the Party to participate in the Convention's institutional structure, thereby participation in decision making process under the Water Convention framework (e.g., adoption of decisions, elections of members of the bodies). This involvement fosters collaborative governance over shared water resources. Becoming a Party allows fostering the implementation of the Convention and its further development, as it can decide on the development of the Convention, be elected to the Convention's governing bodies, lead activities under the Convention, and participate in the development of the Convention's 3-year program of work so that it can better respond to its specific needs. As a Party, it can also utilize the Convention's Implementation Committee, which is available to assist in finding solutions to complex water management issues and to help overcome difficulties in transboundary cooperation.

4.16. Solid International Legal Framework

Joining the Convention provides the Party with a robust legal framework that has been effective in facilitating cooperation between upstream and downstream countries. This framework can help the Party negotiate better terms with its neighbors regarding shared water resources, ensuring fair usage and protection against harm. In addition, tools and guidance developed under the Convention can be applied to support negotiations, such as the Practical Guide for the Development of Agreements or Other Arrangements for Transboundary Water Cooperation [8].

4.17. Advice and Sharing of Experience

Parties benefit from guidance documents and best practices developed under the Convention. It encourages sharing experiences and technical knowledge, and access to expert advice can enhance parties' capacity to manage their water resources effectively. Utilizing the framework of the Convention and its experience of over 30 years could be beneficial in assisting any Party in strengthening its capacity for water negotiation through the Convention's legal, technical, and political activities, offering a long-term framework for continuous support. Blue Peace Middle East (BPME) countries have been benefiting and contributing to the exchange of experience under the Convention since 2012.

5. Obligations of Parties under the 1992 UN Water Convention: [9]

1. Prevent, control, and reduce transboundary Impact

Parties must take all appropriate measures to prevent, control, and reduce any transboundary impact, including impacts on human health, water resources, and ecosystems.

2. Ensure reasonable and equitable use of transboundary waters

Parties must use transboundary waters equitably and reasonably, taking particular account of their transboundary character, and managed in an ecologically sound and rational manner.

3. Conservation and ecological restoration

Parties must conserve and, where necessary, restore ecosystems related to transboundary waters.

4. Concrete measures (Article 3)

Parties must adopt legal, administrative, economic, financial, and technical measures — for example, emission limits based on best available technology, water-quality objectives, environmental impact assessment, contingency planning, and best environmental practices for reducing diffuse pollution (especially from agriculture).

5. Research and development (Article 5)

Parties cooperate in researching effective techniques to prevent, control, and reduce transboundary impacts.

6. Information to the public (Article 16)

Parties must make available to the public information on the condition of transboundary waters, the measures taken, and their effectiveness.

7. Conclude specific agreements (Article 9)

Riparian Parties must enter into bilateral or multilateral agreements (or adapt existing ones) covering the waters they share, and establish joint bodies — such as river commissions — to implement them. The Convention is a framework instrument, so these basin-specific agreements operationalize it.

8. Consultations (Article 10)

Riparian Parties hold consultations based on reciprocity, good faith, and good-neighborliness at the request of any of them.

9. Joint monitoring and assessment (Article 11)

Parties must jointly monitor the condition of shared waters, including agreeing on pollution parameters and pollutants to be regularly monitored.

10. Exchange of information (Article 13)

Parties must exchange reasonably available data on environmental conditions, emission/monitoring data, measures taken, permits, etc. (Confidentiality of industrial/commercial secrets and intellectual property may be invoked.)

11. Warning and alarm systems (Article 14)

Parties must establish coordinated systems for communicating about critical situations, such as accidental pollution, floods, and ice drifts.

12. Mutual assistance (Article 15)

Parties must notify affected States without delay in emergencies and provide mutual assistance upon request.

13. Dispute Settlement (Article 22)

If a dispute arises, the Parties seek a solution through negotiation. Parties may also accept, by written declaration, the compulsory jurisdiction of either the International Court of Justice or arbitration.

6. Steps to join the 1992 UN Water Convention:

To be a Party to the Water Convention, some steps are mandatory such as depositing the instrument of accession signed by an authorized official at the UN Treaty Section. However, the accession process to the Water Convention usually includes four major steps:

Step 1: Preliminary discussion and expression of interest by the Ministry in charge of water.

This step may include:

1. Nomination of focal points and participation in activities under the Convention.
2. Discussion on the Convention, article by article, by technical and legal services in order to establish the steps required for compliance with the Convention's provisions.
3. Presentation on the Convention and discussion among relevant departments of the Ministry.
4. Sending a letter to the secretariat expressing the country's interest in accession (Annex 1).

Step 2: Broader discussion involving relevant sectoral ministries and the Ministry of Foreign Affairs, as well as other relevant actors.

This step may include:

1. Discussions in an informal or formal framework (by establishing an interministerial committee or a working group).
2. Preparation of a list of questions and topics related to the benefits and opportunities derived from accession to the Convention, to be discussed during a national workshop

Step 3: National workshop on the Water Convention.

The national workshop is an occasion to discuss the benefits of the Convention and the challenges of implementation among key actors (relevant sectoral ministries,

Ministry of Foreign Affairs, Parliament, Office of the Prime Minister, basin organizations, civil society, etc.), as well as experts on the Water Convention (Water Convention secretariat, international experts), and technical and financial partners.

Step 4: Undertaking the formal procedure for the ratification of treaties (for accession).

This procedure varies depending on the country, but requires close cooperation between the Ministry in charge of water, the Ministry of Foreign Affairs, the Office of the Prime Minister, Parliament, the Office of the President, and the Water Convention secretariat. It culminates with the deposit of the instrument of accession with the Treaty Section of the United Nations Secretariat in New York.

Can a State intending to become a Party to the Water Convention formulate a reservation concerning some of the provisions of the Convention?

The Water Convention is silent on reservations (the Convention itself does address reservations specifically, leaving that issue unmentioned). The general regime of the law of treaties and the 1969 Vienna Convention on the Law of Treaties would thus apply: A State may formulate a reservation when acceding to the Water Convention, but reservations that go against the object and purpose of the Convention would be inadmissible. As of May 2026, only one Party has made a reservation at the time of ratification.

- Reservation: Countries do not fully accept one or some specific parts of the Convention provisions.

What are the consequences for a Party that decides to withdraw from the Water Convention?

The Water Convention expressly regulates the procedure for withdrawal. Under Article 27, a Party may withdraw at any time after three years from the date on which the Convention entered into force for that Party, by giving written notification to the

Depositary; the withdrawal takes effect on the ninetieth day after receipt of that notification.

7. Who can provide help during the accession process?

The Water Convention secretariat, the Bureau (a small group of representatives from countries that are Parties to the Convention), Parties to the Convention, and Convention partners can help in the accession process. This includes:

- A. Replying to questions from countries seeking clarification of the provisions of the Convention.
- B. If needed and subject to the availability of resources, the secretariat can also co-organize and support a national workshop on the Convention.
- C. The secretariat can also share Convention materials (including the text of the Convention, publications, brochures, and standard presentations) with the country preparing for accession.
- D. The secretariat can help the country prepare for accession by establishing contact with a country that has recently become a Party to share experiences on the accession process and the first steps in implementing the Convention.
- E. Assistance can be provided by the Convention's Implementation Committee (e.g., by responding to questions related to clarification of the Convention's provisions) and by the Parties to the Convention (e.g., through their participation in national workshops on the Convention).
- F. Should support from the Water Convention secretariat be required, an official letter expressing the country's interest in the Water Convention can be sent by the Minister in charge of water or the Minister of Foreign Affairs to the secretariat in order to facilitate such support.

In addition to the Water Convention secretariat, many international organizations (other United Nations Regional Commissions such as Economic and Social Commission for Western Asia (ESCWA), regional economic organizations, and many river basin organizations) support countries on their road to accession to the Convention.

8. Lessons Learned from Iraq's Accession in 2023 to the 1992 UN Water Convention

- a) Use accession as an entry point for inter-ministerial coordination.

Iraq's accession to the 1992 UN Water Convention demonstrates its willingness to engage more systematically with the principles of international water cooperation. One important lesson is that accession can provide a useful platform for strengthening coordination among national institutions. In Iraq's case, the establishment of an Inter-Ministerial Committee on the Water Convention helped bring together the Ministry of Water Resources, the Ministry of Foreign Affairs, and other relevant institutions around the accession process and its follow-up. While the long-term effectiveness of this mechanism will depend on continued political commitment, institutional capacity, and implementation, it represents an important step toward more coordinated decision-making on transboundary water issues [9].

- b) Link accession to a national dialogue, consultations, and stakeholder engagement from the outset.

Iraq's accession process was accompanied by national dialogue and public events, including the Third Baghdad International Water Conference, which helped communicate the objectives and potential benefits of joining the Convention. Such engagement is important because accession is not only a legal act but also a diplomatic and institutional process that requires awareness, political support, and coordination among stakeholders. In this sense, national consultations can help build ownership of the Convention's principles and create a basis for future cooperation among government agencies, experts, and other relevant actors [10].

- c) Use accession to identify institutional and legal gaps.

Accession to the Water Convention can also serve as an opportunity for countries to reflect on existing institutional, legal, and policy gaps related to transboundary water management. In Iraq, the accession process highlighted the importance of aligning national procedures, coordination mechanisms, and water governance practices with international standards. However, accession alone does not automatically close these

gaps. Rather, it creates a framework through which future reforms may be discussed, prioritized, and gradually implemented.

d) Benefit from technical support and peer exchange under the Water Convention.

The Water Convention provides opportunities for technical cooperation, peer learning, and exchange of experience among Parties. Iraq's twinning initiative with Kazakhstan, launched in 2025 under the framework of the Convention, is a relevant example. Through this initiative, Iraq may benefit from Kazakhstan's experience in transboundary water cooperation, particularly in areas such as data exchange, water diplomacy, institutional coordination, and capacity development. Such exchanges should be viewed as supportive tools that can inform Iraq's future policy and institutional development, rather than as immediate solutions to complex regional water challenges [12].

e) Strengthen national capacity through training and workshops.

Another lesson from Iraq's experience is the importance of building institutional capacity soon after accession. National workshops and training sessions can help government officials better understand the Convention's principles, procedures, and tools. In Iraq, such activities contributed to raising awareness among relevant officials and supported discussions on data management, inter-ministerial coordination, and implementation requirements. These activities are important preparatory steps, although their practical impact will depend on sustained follow-up and integration into national decision-making processes [13].

f) Frame accession within broader climate change and water security priorities.

Iraq's accession also reflects the country's recognition that transboundary water cooperation is closely linked to climate change adaptation, drought management, and long-term water security. Rising temperatures, declining water availability, and recurrent droughts have increased the urgency of coordinated responses. By joining the Convention, Iraq has signaled to regional partners and international organizations that it is committed to addressing water security challenges through cooperation and

dialogue. This may help strengthen confidence among international partners and create opportunities for technical and financial support aligned with national priorities [14].

g) Accession can support regional cooperation and diplomatic engagement.

Iraq's accession to the Water Convention represents an important diplomatic signal of its commitment to cooperation on shared water resources. Rather than immediately transforming regional water relations, accession should be understood as a step that strengthens Iraq's position as a constructive actor in regional water diplomacy. It shows a willingness to engage with neighboring countries through internationally recognized principles, including equitable and reasonable utilization, cooperation, information exchange, and the prevention of significant harm. This can contribute to confidence-building and may encourage broader regional dialogue over time [11].

h) Accession demonstrates commitment to international standards.

Iraq's accession to the 1992 UN Water Convention demonstrates its commitment to internationally recognized standards of cooperation, transparency, and sustainable management of shared water resources. This commitment is important not only for water governance but also for Iraq's broader diplomatic positioning. It can help reassure regional partners, international organizations, donors, and potential investors that Iraq is seeking to address water challenges through rules-based cooperation and institutional stability. However, the credibility of this commitment will depend on continued implementation, effective coordination, and practical engagement with neighboring countries.

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